

MERITS OF SOLO PERFORMERS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF KARAKALPAK SINGING ART

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10893472>

Abstract. *The article is devoted to the activities of solo performers which are contributed to the development of the singing art of Karakalpakstan, known for their talent of performing solo songs on the stage of the theater of our Republic in the 50-60s of the twentieth century. Ayymkhan Shamuratova, Tarbiya Zholimbetova, Gulkhan Sherazieva, Arzigul Atamuratova, Tokhta Rakhmanova, Fatima Bekpolatova, Tileusan Akhmedova, Kalbike Matyakubova and Sulyokhan Mambetova as actresses and singers skillfully performed songs from their repertoire, taking a place in the hearts of our people and talking about the first steps of Karakalpak girls in the sphere of art.*

Key words: *Theater, stage master, actress, performance, theatrical characters, folk songs.*

ЗАСЛУГИ СОЛЬНЫХ ИСПОЛНИТЕЛЕЙ В РАЗВИТИИ КАРАКАЛПАКСКОГО ПЕВЧЕСКОГО ИСКУССТВА

Аннотация. *Статья посвящена деятельности сольных исполнителей, внесших свой вклад в развитие певческого искусства Каракалпакстана, известных своим талантом исполнения сольных песен на сцене театра нашей республики в 50-60-е годы XX века. Айымхан Шамуратова, Тарбия Жолимбетова, Гульхан Шеразиева, Арзигуль Атамуратова, Тохта Рахманова, Фатима Бекполатова, Тилеусан Ахмедова, Калбике Матякубова и Сулѣхан Мамбетова как актрисы и певицы умело исполнили песни из своего репертуара, заняв место в сердцах нашего народа и заговорив о первых шагах каракалпакских девушек в искусстве.*

Ключевые слова: *Театр, мастер сцены, актриса, спектакль, театральные персонажи, народные песни.*

1. Relevance.

Each nation's own culture and art is one of the main factors that determine its value as a nation. Humanity came into being, using all its potential, constantly searching for creativity, creation, creativity, observation, it gets aesthetic pleasure, and in this process it rises spiritually. Every nation occupies a strong place in world civilization due to the power of its culture and art.

2.Methods and level of study: As our country continues to further strengthen its place and importance in the world arena, further development of national culture, creation of a new history of new Uzbekistan, preservation and promotion of tangible and intangible cultural heritage masterpieces, further popularization of folk art and amateur art, ensuring active integration of our country into the world cultural space, implemented systematic measures aimed at innovative development of culture and art.

As a clear example of this, a series of Resolutions and Decrees adopted by the head of our state on "Development of the field of culture and art", "On measures to further increase the role and influence of culture and art in the life of society" opens the door to huge opportunities

necessary for the development of the field. From this point of view, in order to introduce the creative activities of our performers who contributed to the development of Karakalpak singing art to today's youth, we should pay special attention to their activities.

3. Research results:

In the 50-80 years of the XX century, Karakalpakstan occupied a special place in the activities of solo performers in the development of singing art. Of these, Ayimkhan Shamuratova received the title of "people's artist of the USSR" in 1968. Along with playing the main roles in the Karakalpak State Theater, it also sang songs of fraternal peoples.

In the 50-60 years of the XX century, the upbringing of solo singers was known by Jolimbetova (1917-1963), Gulkhan Sherazieva (1920-1978), Arzigul Atamuratova (1923-2017), Rachmanova (1934), Fatima Bekpolatova, Tileuhan Akhmedova, Suliukhan Matyakubova and Suliukan Mambetova. They took a deep place in the heart of the people through their skillfully performed songs in their repertoire. National artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan Gulkhan Sherozieva, along with playing the main role in musical performances, inherited Karakalpak folk songs in her repertoire.

National artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan Arzigul Atamuratova has devoted more than 40 years of her life to the development of the art of Karakalpakstan. Arzigul Atamuratova "Dembermes", "Eshbay". She performed the songs "Ceti asirim", "Bes perde", "Bahar suygen yar", "today we are in the bosom of Bakhit", "Tang samallari", "nøkis gulleri", "bagman girl", "Yar-yar".

In the 60-80s of the XX century, Karakalpak girls, known for their tender voice, made folk songs known to the world. In the days of literature and culture of Karakalpakstan, which took place in Moscow in 1959, Gulparshin Sirimbetova performed the song "Døryasan". The songs "Dembermes", "Nalish", "Dostima", "my ways" by the owner of istedad Tamara Dorshumova remained in the people's memory as indelible Navos.

In the 60s and 70s of the XX century, an excellent talent Dao'itbay Kayipov for seven years of his work received a place in the heart of the Karakalpak people with his unique songs, sonorous voice.

In the 80s of the XX century, processed variants of Karakalpak national songs appeared in the variety direction. The services of Dautboy Kayipov, Zamira Khozhanazarova, who raised the Karakalpak variety by one step, were great in it. Z. Khajanazarova "Anajanim", "talqin", "who was Janim jaqsi køresen? the word G.Music of Shamuratova D.Janabaeva. "In which did he eat love?Performing arias from the musical drama" shagalas", "Bahar Samali", "Kelmediq", "Magan kelip ket", "Tuo'ilgan jer", "Tahirlik", "Berdaq" enriched Karakalpak national singing art.

These two talents became known to the country for their short life with the art of Karakalpak execution and were regarded as "unfading stars", revered among the people. The repertoire of Bayram Matjanov (1940-2020), known for his 37 years of work, which contributed to the development of Karakalpak singing art, with a pleasant voice, lively feelings and a stage culture that attracts listeners, is popularly known as a rich innovator performer. B. Matzhanov paid special attention to the synchronicity of music with the meaning of words, paying special attention to the issue of choosing a repertoire. B.Matzhanov introduced the art of Karakalpak singing to fraternal

peoples and received the title of people's artist of Uzbekistan, Bashkirdistan, Karakalpakstan and state awards.

National artist of Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Karakalpakstan Kamiljon Otaniyozov said among his students that Atajon Khudayshukurov "on the other side of the Amudarya there is a talented young man who is distinguished from his peers by the voice given by Allah. It is said by his father Khudayshukurov. Both tomorrow's Nightingale and pride of the bust of art will be that young man." Father Khudayshukurov has been working as a solo singer in the Karakalpak State Philharmonic since 1963. Along with classical songs, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Karakalpak, Kazakh and Kyrgyz folk songs were included in his work. O.Khudayshukurov, along with the singer, musician, is also known as the composer of more than 300 songs, such as "your Mujgon", "one in the universe", "my first love". O.Khudayshukurov was attractive, timbre, with a smooth and sonorous voice in all curtains. It was not for nothing that such qualities in his songs as passion, enthusiasm and enthusiasm, and depth in content took a deep place in the hearts of the audience."

Bazarboy Nodirov, Gulparshin Sirimbetova, Bibiraba Utepbergenova, Tursingul Kayipnazarova, Tursinbay Palimbetov, Utebay Temirkhanov, Tamara Doshumova, Marjangul Tileomuratova, Sveta Shinikulova, Makhset Matekov, Hanzada Paloanova, Perikhan Alibekova, who created a unique school in the national singing art of Karakalpakstan in the 70-80s of the XX century left an indelible mark on national singing art with.

Ida Rafikova, Ilyich Khodjametov, Maxset Khozhaniyazov, Davlet Atajanov, Kenesboy Serzhanov, Gulhatiysha Ayimbetova, Bazargul Karimova, Dalibay Mambetmuratov, Mirzagul Sapaeva, Rosa Kutekeeva brought the Karakalpak national singing art to a new level. The fact that the talented singer Maxset Khozhaniyazov was a prize winner at the International Festival in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, a laureate of the Central Asian Festival of vocalists took an important place in the world recognition of the art of Karakalpak singing.

Ilich Khodjametov also played a great role in the development of the variety route in Karakalpakstan. I.Khodjametov organized the revyu variety ensemble "forty girls" under the Karakalpak State Philharmonic named after Berdak. From the singers of the ensemble Bayarkina, L.Koshan (Russia), I.Vakhlakov (Baku) I.Khadjametav, Q.Allayarov, M.Tileomuratova, O.Temirkhanov, D.Mambetmuratov, M.Artikova, Z.Kamalova, G.Monteeva, M.Tajigalieva, Zamira and Inkar Khojanazarova, V.Chaban from dancers S.Dospanova, Zarema and Lola Rafikova, I.Loseva, I.Shvalova, I.Number, I.Li, A.Kalikovas made a great contribution to the development of the variety genre in the art of Karakalpakstan. The first time the ensemble performed works from the repertoire of foreign performers, Uzbek, Karakalpak folk songs and musics. In particular, the songs "Mukhabbatihnan", "Tashkent evening", "Black Willows", "Tuugan jerge", "Shagala", "Tolqin" are preserved in the people's memory to this day. In 1981, the ensemble "Forty Girls" was called variety-choreographic Revue, and the artistic director D.M.Tarleev and chief ballet player D. Yusupov was engaged in work.

1981-1982 with the ensemble concert program, they toured South Sakhalin, the Far East, Kamchatka, the Caucasus, Crimea, Moldavia, the Republic of Buryatia, in 1983 in the cities of Magadan, Chita, Ulan-Ude, in 1986 in the republics of Moykop, Ukraine, Vilnius, Riga, Belarus, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan. Especially Muyassar Razzakova, Rosa Qutekeeva, Eliza Aitniyazova contributed to the recognition of Karakalpak opera, folk songs all over the world.

A Republican competition of Bakhshi performers was organized in Tashkent, dedicated to the 100th anniversary of Japaq Bakhshi Shamuratov, at which the Karakalpakstan T.Gurbanov, M.Pirnazarov, young singer a.Aytniyazov won.

In 1992, 11 competitions and Memorial evenings were held dedicated to the anniversaries of art artists. In Particular, Japaq Bakshi Shamuratov, Ayimkhan Shamuratova, A.Khajalepesov, E.Gaspalatav, C.Bekmuratov, D.Qayipov, Z.Festivals of young talented people were organized in memory of Khozhanazarova. The festivals were attended by guests from Tashovuz, Khorezm and Bukhara region of Turkmenistan.

The days of culture of the Republic of Karakalpakstan were held in Tashkent on January 25-29, 1993. During these days of culture, literary and art artists of Karakalpakstan presented concert programs at the State Theater and stage of Tashkent City. A group of Karakalpak artists are awarded honorary titles of the Republic of Uzbekistan by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of These, T.Kayipbergenov "people's writer of Uzbekistan", G.Aymbetova, M.Sapayeva, R.Saparova and B.Kayipovs title "Honored artist Of The Republic of Uzbekistan", chief correspondent of the magazine "Aral girls" G.Esemuratova is awarded the title of " honored cultural figure of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

2007 Actress of Karakalpak state musical theater Sarbinaz Annakulova became laureate of the Nihal prize. As a theater actress, she starred in the play" Alpomish " in Gulbarshin, S.Aysanem in the play by hojaniyazov "Syymegenge syykenbe", K.Rakhmanov in the play" Yar diydari " created the images of the main character in Maqpal and many other performances .

In 2008, Variety singer late Rashid Khojasov, the winner of the" Nihol "award, was highly appreciated for his service as a real talent and was awarded the honorable title" Honored artist of the Republic of Karakalpakstan".

In recent years, Aygul Nadirova has been noticed for her skills in performing folk songs and national songs of the variety direction. In his performance, folk songs were sung, modernizing the songs "Nalish" and "walk girls", N.Muhammedinov, "Yor-yor I say", J.Shamuratov's songs" Yestelik seven oramal " performed with high skill in the national style.

Independence has taken an important place in the recognition of our talented youth on the world stage. In particular, the Honored artist of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Jenisbek Piyazov, with his special talent for creativity in the opera direction, was able to receive the "Nihol" award in 2007. Jenisbek Piyazov took part in competitions held in such countries as France, Spain, Portugal, Russia, Malaysia, Kazakhstan. In 2010, in accordance with the presidential decree, he was awarded the Medal of Fame. J.Piyazov's tireless work in introducing national art to the world was highly appreciated, in 2014 he was awarded the title of "Honored artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan", in 2021-"people's artist of the Republic of Uzbekistan".

During the independence period, the folklore and ethnographic ensemble "AMU wave " occupies an important place in the supply of musical treasures of the Karakalpak people to generations. People's artist of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan Gylkhatiysha Ayimbetova, honored artists of the Republic of Karakalpakstan Bakhtiyar Yesemuratov, Salamat Kalibekov, Sultan Kasekyev showed their abilities in performing folk and modern songs from the members of the ensemble.

The establishment of the State prize named after Zulfiya by the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on June 10, 1999 took a huge place in the material and spiritual support of the creative and active people of gifted youth. To date, more than 20 girls have won the Zulfiya State Prize in the Republic of Karakalpakstan since 2000.

The "germination" award opened a wide path to the identification of young talent and their further improvement from creative abilities. The first winner of the award from the Republic of Karakalpakstan was the talented singer Makset Utemuratov. In subsequent years, Dilfuza Bekimbetova, Gulnar Aljanova, Eleonora Qutlibulatova, Gulnaz Utepova, Sarbinaz Annakulova, Jenisbek Piyazov, Rashid Khojasov, Gulbar Abipova, Zhat Bekchanov, Lola Muhammaddinova, G.Akhimbetova, Janibek Piyazov, Adilbek Bakhtibayev, Naorizbek Mahammadiyarov became winners of the "Nihal" prize.

Conclusions:

In the 50s-80s of the 20th century, professional composers were able to contribute to the development of national singing art with new music in the development of Karakalpak music culture. Genisbek Piyazov's services in introducing the opera genre to the world in the art of singing, as a result, talented talents are emerging after him. In the development of the pop genre in Karakalpakstan, the activity of the Karakalpak State Folklore Ethnographic Ensemble "Amu Wave" marked the beginning of a new era in art. At the same time, the Ayqulash juldyzlyry ensemble had a great role in the development of dance art in the republic during the years of independence, and these artists won a number of achievements in the national dance art in the Central Asian republics and at festivals of Eastern dances. During the period of independence, G. Allambergenova, Z. Sharipova, T. Qalliev, G. Akhymbetova contributed to the introduction of the Karakalpak national art of charity to the peoples of the world. The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 10, 2021 "On additional measures related to the preparation for the Second International Bakhshiki Art Festival and the creation of favorable conditions for the development of the art of Bakhshiki" opened the door of opportunities for the development of national Bakhshiki art at the national and international level.

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